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Importance of Black Holes and White Holes in the Universe

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ABSTRACT

In the entire world few elements and materials are not degradable; these are called waste handling materials, but the problem is how to biodegrade these materials. In this paper this problem can be rectified easily with the help of the black hole energy transformation from 1 CG to another lower sky or CG, as this is the safest and fastest method of delivering the waste handling materials and biodegradables. The idea and concept are too difficult to understand and analyze, but the process is too convenient and easy. The biggest headache is the problem of materials like plastic, which is not biodegradable, so this type of material also can be delivered to the lower sky through black holes. All waste-handling materials can be transported to the Nadir Adho Disha direction, lower sky, through the CG place location as a black hole. The entire universe is composed of 14 CGs, as these are the main center places through these 7 upper skies and 7 lower skies, and transferring the energy as fire, power, heat, rain, light, air, materials, 1D, 2D, and sheaths, so all these physical things as a single sheath of the human body are delivered to the lower sky as the nadir side direction through the CG called a black hole. From this achievement one can balance the planet Earth well and good.

Keywords: *Black hole, white hole, CG, zenith, nadir, lower sky, upper sky, biodegradable materials, waste handling materials, plastic*

INTRODUCTION

In the entire world, all types of materials are available, which are made from degradable, biodegradable, or non-degradable materials. So these constitute the environmental pollution in the form of air pollution, water pollution, and so on. This is waste handling material and can be delivered to the source place of origin through the black hole concept, which will be best captured as media to deliver the bottom side of the nadir side direction at all. There will be energy, power, and other physical, chemical, or biological quantities that can be transferred through black holes and white holes. The white hole is the main source of positive energy quantities and helps to maintain ecosystem balance. One of the best sources of physical energy is from the lower sky, or Nadir direction, as adho will transfer the quantity through the white hole concept, as the media is the earth planet. That's why maintaining the equilibrium as a balance of these CG sky levels enhances the ecosystem environment. Meanwhile, one can control the climate as and when required by capturing polluted air and sending it back to the lower sky as CG media only. The 1D and 2D human body sheaths are as ancestors will be looking at them: too dirty, strange, peculiar, and ugly. The main reason is unhealthy air for breathing and impure water. The sound waves have a definite frequency, but light waves have both frequency and wavelength. The dual nature of materials can be made as to transfer its energy through the way of CG to the lower sky as the Nadir side direction as black holes. Also, till modern intellectual approaches, one had to conclude that only matter exists in 3 states, but after deep study and analysis, matter exists in several phases, up to 14 also. White holes are the major sources of positive energy creation as well as transfer to the planet Earth only. The waste disposal can be easily made as the concept of black hole. [1-10]

LITERATURE REVIEW [11-20]

1. Nemanja Protic et al, "Black holes and parallax gaps: the contemporary graphic noir of Charles Burns's Black Hole" proposed that Charles Burns combines noir's current of symbolic unmasking with the visual elements found in the subgenre of body-horror to explore the insistence of the material real upon the daily lived experience of his text's protagonists, suburban high-school students who function as the contemporary correlatives of noir's losers and loners. In doing so, Burns critiques the masculine power structures implicit in the normative world of suburban America – as well as in the genres of noir and horror
2. Katie Robertson "Black Hole Thermodynamics: A Crisis of Identity" proposed that point out differences between the quantities associated to black holes and the quantities of ordinary thermal systems, like cups of tea and boxes of gas. How can we say black hole entropy is thermodynamic entropy when there are these differences? In this paper, I show to what extent the increasingly popular tool of functionalism can be used to understand the claim that S_{BH} is S_{TD} . The Black Hole Zeroth Law The surface gravity of a stationary black hole is constant over its entire surface. The Black Hole First Law A change in the total mass of the black hole is determined in a fixed way by changes in its area, angular momentum, and electric charge, so that the total quantity is conserved. The Black Hole Second Law The area of the event horizon of a black hole cannot decrease.
3. Branka Pecotic "The 'black hole' in the inner universe" proposed that If the experience of relating to the 'black hole' in the object happens early and in such a powerful way that the child's energy feels insufficient to defend against it in

any way, then the fear of annihilation becomes so strong that it may lead to the wiping out of the whole internal universe in order to escape its deadly gravitational pull. Only when a different kind of relationship gets internalized, through therapy, with an object that contains and returns life and energy, can the mind grow enough to be able to communicate the other, darker side of the relationship from which it has closed itself away.

4. Robert C. Thompson “The “Black Hole” Night Visual Approach: Calculated Approach Paths Resulting From Flying a Constant Visual Vertical Angle to Level and Upslope Runways” proposed that This report specifically investigates the second factor in detail, calculating numerous constant vertical angle (CVA) flight paths including the effects of approach length, starting altitude, glideslope angle, runway length, runway slope, runway hump, dip, tilt, or curve, and two commonly encountered approach obstacle clearance surfaces (OCS). Comparisons are made to limited data from published Boeing 727 simulator experiments. Constant vertical angle (CVA) visual flight paths are calculated, showing the effects of starting altitude and distance, runway length, shape, and slope. Results are compared to published simulator studies. CVA flight tendency over level terrain cannot cause flight into the ground miles distant from the airport, except approaching an upsloping runway. Approach strategies for light aircraft to avoid this psychological phenomenon are indicated. A template for accident investigation use is illustrated
5. Senjaya, David “Cored Navarro-Frenk-White dark matter halo: novel black hole solution, energy condition, optical properties, quasinormal modes and thermodynamics.” proposed that The stability of photon orbits is analyzed using the Lyapunov exponent, which we relate to the imaginary part of the massless quasinormal modes in the eikonal limit. We also investigate the thermodynamic behavior of the black hole–dark matter system by evaluating the mass function, entropy, temperature, heat capacity, Gibbs free energy and the entropy to assess both local and global stability. Overall, our results demonstrate that the surrounding dark matter halo significantly influences the black hole's properties, enhancing its thermodynamic stability and allowing the possibility of phase transitions.
6. Volovik, G. E. “Extended Tsallis–Cirto Entropy for Black and White Holes” the composition rule remains the same, with the only difference being that instead of entropy it contains the entropy modulus. The same non-extensive composition rule is obtained for the entropy of the Reissner–Nordström black hole. This entropy is formed by the positive entropy of the outer horizon and the negative entropy of the inner horizon. The model of the black hole formed by black hole atoms with Planck-scale mass is also extended to include the negative entropy of white holes
7. Trupp, Andreas “Traversing a black-and-white hole in free fall and rise” proposed that a traverse of a Black-and-White Hole (through a shaft in the interior of the central, spherical body) in free radial fall and rise is described by the Schwarzschild metric without any ambiguity. In other words, all Black Holes can also be White Holes. The relativity principle, according to which both the freely falling/rising observer Alice and a second observer Bob (sitting outside of the gravity field) have to measure the same temporal interval for the complete trip
8. Kardashev, N. et al “Observational effects in black and white holes (dynamical wormholes)” proposed that

The passage of matter through the wormhole in these models is possible only in one direction (from past to future). All models are considered under the assumption of spherical symmetry. It is shown that all models without a throat do not violate the null energy condition. The model of a Reissner-Nordström black hole containing no singularities inside the horizon has been constructed. The trajectories of particles and light rays passing from one universe into another have been constructed for the simplest Reissner-Nordström black and white hole. Distinctive features have been found for the images of objects from another universe observed through such objects. The characteristics of these images are compared with those for ordinary wormholes

9. Pekker, Mikhail et al “On the Possible Nature of White Holes” proposed that About 50 years ago, on the basis of an analysis of Einstein's equations, Novikov showed that in the universe, along with black holes, radiation from which is impossible, there must be white holes, which cannot be reached from outside. Moreover, pure black holes or pure white holes cannot exist. In other words, all matter drawn into a black hole splashes out either into the neighboring universe, for which it is white, or a so-called wormhole is formed—a bridge along which matter drawn into a black hole from one area of the universe splashes out through a white hole into another. In the astrophysical community, quasars and powerful short-lived bursts of gamma radiation are considered as candidates for a white hole. The question of the existence (or rather the possibility of detection) of white holes is open, since at the edge of the event horizon of a white hole, the density of matter should reach such a high value that black holes

should form, which "eat" the matter flowing out of the white.

10. Oeckl, Robert “A predictive framework for quantum gravity and black hole to white hole transition” proposed that quantum theory and general relativity has long hampered efforts to find a quantum theory of gravity. The recently proposed positive formalism for quantum theory purports to remove this incompatibility. We showcase the power of the positive formalism by applying it to the black hole to white hole transition scenario that has been proposed as a possible effect of quantum gravity. We show how the characteristic observable of this scenario, the bounce time, can be predicted within the positive formalism, while a traditional S-matrix approach fails at this task. Our result also involves a conceptually novel use of positive operator valued measures.

METHODS OF FINDINGS

As there is no time in black hole and many years can be lived as one of the past stage of existence of human life in one of the dimensions as 1d, 2d, or nd etc. The time can fix the human age in earth planet as solar based only, while in other sky as black hole and white hole the time fails it.[21-27]

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Yes, one can deliver a quantity of energy, a wave, or a particle to the lower sky as Nadir or ADHO direction through the concept of a black hole through the media as the earth planet. The waste disposal can be easily made as the concept of a black hole. Also, one can speed up the particle to be equivalent to light speed such that the effect is first and the cause is second, then delivery transportation can be made easily.

CONCLUSION

- In the entire world few elements and materials are not degradable; these are

called waste handling materials, but the problem is how to biodegrade these materials.

- In this paper this problem can be rectified easily with the help of the black hole energy transformation from 1 CG to another lower sky or CG, as this is the safest and fastest method of delivering the waste handling materials and biodegradables.
- The entire universe is composed of 14 CGs, as these are the main centre places through these 7 upper skies and 7 lower skies, and transferring the energy as fire, power, heat, rain, light, air, materials, 1D, 2D, and sheaths, so all these physical things as a single sheath of the human body are delivered to the lower sky as the nadir side direction through the CG called a black hole
- There will be energy, power, and other physical, chemical, or biological quantities that can be transferred through black holes and white holes. The white hole is the main source of positive energy quantities and helps to maintain ecosystem balance
- The waste disposal can be easily made as the concept of black hole.
- Yes, one can deliver a quantity of energy, a wave, or a particle to the lower sky as Nadir or ADHO direction through the concept of a black hole through the media as the earth planet.
- The waste disposal can be easily made as the concept of a black hole. Also, one can speed up the particle to be equivalent to light speed such that the effect is first and the cause is second, then delivery transportation can be made easily.

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